

**A TRIPTYCH OF BASSISTS: EXPLORING THE ARTISTRY AND
TECHNIQUE OF THREE DISTINCTIVE JAZZ BASSISTS**

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Thematic Paper
entitled
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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the repertoire of the Graduate Jazz Bass recital performed as a tribute to the three renowned jazz bassists: Paul Chambers, Jimmy Garrison, and Christian McBride. Since the three bass players represent different periods and have different bass line characteristics; four compositions (“Dear Old Stockholm,” “Soul Eyes,” “Resolution,” and “My Favorite Things”) were selected as the scope of this study.

The research methodology of this study included the production of bass transcriptions of the compositions recorded by the three renowned jazz bassists, followed by a comprehensive analysis of the transcriptions to explore the artistry and technique of the musicians. The creative component of this research yielded five bass exercises that any jazz bass player can perform to apprehend the characteristics of these three legendary jazz bassists. The Graduate Jazz Bass recital was performed at A113, College of Music, Mahidol University, on March 14, 2024, from 12:00 p.m. to 1:00 p.m.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE THEMATIC PAPER

This thematic paper focuses on four jazz standard songs played by three different period representative jazz bassists, including Paul Chambers, Jimmy Garrison, and Christian McBride. By analyzing how the three bassists applied the scales and rhythm to the solo and bass line of the four songs, the results of this research not only provided a deeper understanding of the performance characteristics of the three bassists but also achieved the purpose of imitating and learning. After summarizing the performance characteristics of the three bassists, any jazz bass players may apply those characteristics to practice and performance and gradually develop personal styles to improve jazz bass playing skills.

KEYWORDS: JAZZ DOUBLE BASS / PAUL CHAMBERS / JIMMY GARRISON /
CHRISTIAN MCBRIDE

96 pages

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background Information

The 1950s marked a significant period for jazz in American music history, yielding innumerable influential jazz artists and compositions. During this era, jazz evolved from bebop, with cool jazz and hard bop emerging as prominent styles. In the early 1950s, jazz retained its traditional characteristics of improvisation, polyphony, and strong rhythm. However, new elements gradually found their way into the genre. For instance, piano-dominated trios like the Bill Evans Trio and Oscar Peterson Trio gained prominence during this time (Rosenthal, 1993, p. 26). With ever fewer players in jazz ensembles, bass assumed a more prominent role by taking on additional functions. Notably, musicians such as Ray Brown, Paul Chambers, Scott LaFaro, and Percy Heath developed their own styles while fulfilling rhythmic responsibilities within the ensemble (Martin & Waters, 2006, p. 152).

The mid-to-late 1950s also witnessed the release of several classic albums and iconic performances, leaving an indelible mark on jazz history. Four experimental albums released in 1959 significantly influenced jazz development: Miles Davis's *Kind of Blue*, Ornette Coleman's *The Shape of Jazz to Come*, Charles Mingus's *Mingus Ah Um*, and Dave Brubeck's *Time Out*. This decade was characterized by immense energy and creativity that not only inherited features from bebop but also paved the way for developments in the following decade (Latour, 2012, p. 4).

Later on, in the 1960s, jazz expanded beyond the boundaries of traditional forms, introducing more experimentation and personalization. Free jazz icons such as Ornette Coleman began to explore new pathways of musical expression that went beyond tradition and conventional structures (Babin, 2021, p. 1). The use of non-traditional harmonies and the absence of a steady pulse or meter—sometimes even abandoning harmonic instruments like piano and guitar—pushed improvisation to its limits. During this period, bass and drum roles were also transformed; they no longer

played solely for timekeeping but often participated in collective improvisation, where interaction between band members was emphasized. The 60s marked a time of social upheaval in America. It was reflected through jazz music, with many musicians expressing their concerns about racial issues through songs like “Fables of Faubus” by Charles Mingus, “Alabama” by John Coltrane, and “Freedom Suite” by Sonny Rollins (Tanner & Megill, 2012, p. 266).

In the contemporary music world, jazz has undergone a remarkable transformation. It is no longer confined to its traditional style but fearlessly embraces elements of rock, funk, hip-hop, and electronic music, thereby diversifying the expression of jazz. This fusion expands the music’s horizons and offers listeners a fresh auditory experience. Regarding musical technique, jazz has made significant breakthroughs. Innovations in harmony, rhythm, and timbre have opened up endless possibilities for musical creation. These innovative techniques enable musicians to convey their emotions and thoughts with greater depth and breadth, resulting in more profound and expansive musical compositions (Pressing, 2002, p. 194).

Yet, contemporary jazz musicians have not overlooked the heritage of traditional music. Renowned artists such as Kurt Rosenwinkel, Tigran Hamasyan, Christian McBride, and Larry Grenadier have reimagined classic jazz pieces. While paying homage to tradition, they skillfully integrate modern elements into these timeless compositions, infusing them with renewed vitality within today's context (Beuttler, 2019, p. 103).

Paul Chambers' melodious arco technique and walking bass line established the foundation for future bassists. Jimmy Garrison further developed this with his robust, spiritually-infused playing, particularly within the context of modal and free jazz. Building upon the legacies of these pioneers, Christian McBride broadened the role of the bass in contemporary jazz by integrating elements from a diverse array of genres. Each bassist has drawn inspiration from and expanded upon the techniques and musical concepts of their predecessors. For instance, McBride frequently acknowledges the influence of past jazz luminaries such as Chambers and Garrison on his own artistry (Chris, 2006). The progression from Chambers to Garrison to McBride exemplifies the ongoing evolution of jazz bass performance, with each musician contributing to the depth and diversity of the genre.

Paul Chambers, Jimmy Garrison, and Christian McBride represent distinct generations of jazz bassists, each making unique contributions to the development and perpetuation of the jazz tradition. Their combined legacy underscores the pivotal role played by the bass in ensembles and its continual innovation within this genre.

1.2 Objectives

The research objectives of this thematic paper are as follows:

- 1) To analyze the bass line played by Paul Chambers, Jimmy Garrison, and Christian McBride in jazz standards of different styles. These three jazz double bass players are representatives of three different periods of hard bop, avant-garde, and contemporary jazz respectively. Analyzing these three players not only helps to understand the style of the bass line in different eras but also illustrates the developmental context of the bass line and connects the three players from the perspective of stylistic evolution.
- 2) To enhance one's ability to master, play, and arrange different jazz standards by five exercises, including playing in a “two-feel” and ballad style, using chromaticism and double stops in bass lines, and practicing in 5/4 to understand their characteristics.

1.3 Scope of Study

As the theme of the author's concert centers on the diverse interpretations by bassists of jazz standards across different eras (1950s, 1960s, and contemporary), four pieces have been carefully selected for performance and analysis, including “Dear Old Stockholm,” “Soul Eyes,” “A Love Supreme Part II: Resolution,” and “My Favorite Things.”

Table 1.1 Recital Repertoire

Title	Repertoires					
	Time signature	Composer	Feel	Album	Label/Year recorded	Performing bassist
“Dear Old Stockholm”	4/4	Traditional	Swing	<i>Bass on Top</i>	Blue Note/1957	Paul Chambers
“Soul Eyes”	4/4	Mal Waldron	Ballad	<i>Coltrane</i>	Impulse! /1962	Jimmy Garrison
“A Love Supreme Part II: Resolution”	4/4	John Coltrane	Swing	<i>A Love Supreme</i>	Impulse! / 1964	Jimmy Garrison
“My Favorite Things”	5/4	Rodgers Charles Rodgers	Swing	<i>Out Here</i>	Mack Avenue/ 2013	Christian McBride

1.4 Expectations

This paper aims to objectively examine the evolution of the jazz bass style by analyzing the performance characteristics of bass masters in different historical periods. By exploring the diversity of jazz, this study aims to improve our understanding and appreciation of various styles of walking bass lines while examining traditional jazz standards in a contemporary context through comprehensive analysis.

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Methods of Bass Analysis

Mike Downes's *The Jazz Bass Line Book* aims to assist jazz musicians in crafting functional, supportive, and aesthetically pleasing bass lines by presenting essential concepts for constructing walking bass lines within various musical forms. These include blues form, rhythm changes form, and playing in a "two-feel" and 3/4-time ballads, among others, that are integral to jazz bassists. Engaging this resource will make musicians more proficient in developing distinctive, individualized bass lines. Furthermore, this publication features numerous exemplary works by renowned artists such as Ray Brown, Ron Carter, Sam Jones, and Paul Chambers, providing valuable insights directly derived from masters' experiences. Additionally, the text introduces specialized terminology elucidating note movements, such as "passing tones," is approached by step and then continues by step in the same direction, "chromatic approach," leads from one note to the very next note, "arpeggio," a broken chord consists of the individual notes of a chord played in a progressively rising or descending order. "Chord tones" refer to the notes that make up the chord, while "sequences" involve the repetition of a motif or a longer melodic (or harmonic) passage at a higher or lower pitch within the same voice (Downes, 2015, p. 7).

Concepts for Bass Soloing by Chuck Sher and Marc Johnson is a comprehensive guide designed to provide aspiring and professional bassists with the tools they need to expand their improvisational skills. The book focuses on various concepts, techniques, and theoretical frameworks that are essential for creating coherent and meaningful solos. Through detailed explanations, musical examples, and exercises, readers can develop a deeper understanding of how to construct compelling bass solos that resonate with both technical proficiency and emotional expression. Furthermore, the authors offer insights into the creative process behind soloing, emphasizing the importance of developing a personal voice while drawing inspiration from diverse

musical traditions. By exploring topics such as melodic development, rhythmic variation, harmonic awareness, and phrasing nuances, this book equips bassists with a versatile toolkit for crafting engaging solos across different genres and musical contexts. In addition to its instructional content, *Concepts for Bass Soloing* also provides historical context and analysis of influential bass soloists throughout music history. This enriches the reader's understanding of the evolution of bass soloing as an art form while offering valuable references for further exploration. Overall, this book serves as an invaluable resource for any bassist looking to elevate their soloing abilities and unlock new levels of creativity in their playing (Sher & Johnson, 1993, p. 3).

The next section delineates the proficiencies demonstrated in the author's concert repertoire and elucidates their application. It is organized into five distinct subsections (2.1.1 through 2.1.5).

2.1.1 Playing in a “two-feel”

Playing in a “two-feel” means playing two notes to the bar or half notes in 4/4 time. It is usual in bass comping, and a two-feel can give songs more of a swing feel. (Downes, 2015, p. 91).

Figure 2.1 Example of playing in “two-feel.”

This is a very common way of playing in different styles, such as swing and ballad. Meanwhile, rhythmic variations can occur, such as changing a half note to two-quarter notes (Downes, 2015, p. 93).

Figure 2.2 Example of replacing a half note with quarter notes.

Additionally, one might change a quarter note to two eighth notes:

Figure 2.3 Example of playing half notes, quarter notes, and eighth notes.

Half notes and quarter notes can be combined:

Figure 2.4 Example of combining half notes and quarter notes.

Syncopated rhythms can also be created:

Figure 2.5 Example of playing a syncopated rhythm.

2.1.2 Playing in Ballad Style

Playing a ballad well is arguably the hardest thing to do in jazz bass performances. Everything bass players play is exposed: the choice of notes, sound intonation, feel, and all the other things that define the quality of one's bass playing. These are some ways to play ballads (Downes, 2015, p. 103).

Triplet feel or 12/8 (or simply swing feel):

Figure 2.6 Example of playing triplet feel in ballad style.

The pulse is the quarter note, but the feel is defined by the underlying eighth note triplet:

Figure 2.7 The feel of triplets in ballad style.

Implied double-time swing:

Figure 2.8 Example of double-time swing.

The underlying feel makes two beats seem like one bar of 4/4, and eighth notes sound like quarter notes at a faster tempo:

Figure 2.9 Rhythmic pattern in double-time swing.

Straight eighths:

Figure 2.10 Straight eighths in ballad style.

The underlying feel is eighth notes, played straight:

Figure 2.11 Rhythmic pattern in straight eighth notes.

2.1.3 Using Chromaticism in Bass Lines

Chromaticism is a common trick in a bass line that adds variation to the walking line and brings a more modern sound. At the same time, it is an effective way to get closer to a target note, as any chord tone can be considered a target note (Sher & Johnson, 1993, p. 23).

Figure 2.12 Using chromaticism in a walking line.

2.1.4 Using Double Stops in Bass Lines

Playing two notes or more at one time on the bass can create a full, rich sound. Here are some examples of playing “double stops” (two notes played together).

Playing in perfect 4ths:

Figure 2.13 Jimmy Garrison riff from “Resolution” (*A Love Supreme*).

Playing in perfect 5ths:

Figure 2.14 Herbie Watts riff from “African Village” (*Time for Tyner*).

Playing in 3rds:

Figure 2.15 “Blue Monk” by Christian McBride.

2.1.5 The Fundamental Concept 5/4 in Jazz Bass Performances

5/4 is signatures of irregular meters, which are widely used in modern jazz. To master the mechanism of irregular meters, one must use a mathematical mode of thinking. One can construct the rhythm of an irregular meter using free combinations of subdivisions constituting the whole, as seen in the following examples of 5/4 meters.

Table 2.1 Basic rhythmic patterns of irregular meters

Time	Harmonic Rhythm	Ostinato
5/4	3+2	
	2+3	

2.2 Background of the Three Subject Bassists

2.2.1 Biography of Paul Chambers

Paul Laurence Dunbar Chambers, Jr. was born on April 11, 1935, in Pittsburgh. The son of Paul Lawrence Chambers and Ann Dunbar, Chambers studied baritone horn in school as a child. When Chambers was eight, his mother passed away, and he went to Detroit to live with his father. There, Chambers studied tuba for a while before taking up the upright bass in 1952, studying with the bassist of the Detroit Symphony Orchestra. Chambers eventually started performing with the Cass Technical High School Symphony Orchestra, occasionally playing baritone saxophone with student ensembles (Larkin, 1992, p. 82).

During this time, Chambers’s interest in jazz music began to grow when he was 15 years old, he became interested in bebop by listening to saxophonist Charlie Parker and pianist Bud Powell. Ray Brown and Oscar Pettiford as bass players were the first influences on Chambers and let him decide to choose double bass, but he was also

impressed by Charlie Mingus's superb rhythms and complex harmonies. Duke Ellington's bassist Jimmy Blanton eventually became Chambers's favorite.

In 1955, Chambers toured with saxophonist Paul Quinichette. After moving to New York in 1955, he played with many musicians, including J.J. Johnson, Kai Winding, Benny Green, George Wallington, Jackie McLean, Donald Byrd, and Art Taylor. After a long period of performance, Chambers's skills improved, and due to his outstanding abilities, McLean introduced him to Miles Davis, with whom he started playing in a quartet (Gridley, 2015, p. 72).

After joining Davis's quartet, Chambers experienced an upturn in his career, recording not only his albums *Chambers' Music*, in 1956 but also several albums with Davis, like *Workin* and *Steamin* etc. *Down Beat Magazine* awarded Chambers a New Star Award for his work on John Coltrane's 1957 album *Blue Train*. (allaboutjazz.com, 2015).

In 1959, *Kind of Blue* was recorded on March 2nd and April 6th. Between these two days, John Coltrane also recorded another album, *Giant Steps*. Due to Paul Chambers recording the bass part for *Kind of Blue*, he was naturally invited to participate in the *Giant Steps* recording (Gridley, 2015, p. 75).

Chambers continued to collaborate with other jazz musicians throughout the 1960s and left Davis's band in 1963, collaborating with Art Blakey on the 1965 album *The Turnaround*. In 1967, he continued with Barry Harris, Sonny Harris, and others as co-musicians, performed in jazz clubs, and released the album *Lesser*.

Paul Chambers died of heroin abuse in 1969 (Wendell, 2010).

2.2.2 Discography

Table 2.2 Paul Chambers' Discography

Period	Album/Artist
1955	<i>Presenting Cannonball Adderley</i> with Julian "Cannonball" Adderley <i>Julian "Cannonball" Adderley</i> with Julian "Cannonball" Adderley <i>Introducing Nat Adderley</i> with Nat Adderley <i>Byrd's Word</i> with Donald Byrd <i>Bennie Green Blows His Horn</i> with Bennie Green <i>The Eminent Jay: Jay Johnson Volume 2</i> with J. J. Johnson <i>Trombone for Two</i> with J. J. Johnson
1956	<i>Chambers' Music</i> <i>Whims of Chambers</i> <i>High Step</i> <i>The Toshiko Trio</i> with Toshiko Akiyoshi <i>Jazzmen of Detroit</i> with Kenny Burrell <i>Introducing Kenny Burrell</i> with Kenny Burrell <i>Miles</i> with Miles Davis <i>Collectors' Items</i> with Miles Davis <i>A Garland of Red</i> with Red Garland <i>Informal Jazz</i> with Elmo Hope <i>Lee Morgan Sextet</i> with Lee Morgan <i>Tenor Madness</i> with Sonny Rollins
1957	<i>Westlake Bounce the Music of John Graas</i> with Philly Joe Jones <i>Bass on Top</i> <i>Paul Chambers Quintet</i> <i>John Jenkins with Kenny Burrell</i> with Kenny Burrell <i>New Formulas from the Jazz Lab</i> with Donald Byrd <i>Sonny's Crib</i> with Sonny Clark

Table 2.2 Paul Chambers' Discography (cont.)

Period	Album/Artist
1957	<i>Sonny Clark Trio</i> with Sonny Clark <i>Coltrane</i> with John Coltrane <i>'Round About Midnight</i> with Miles Davis <i>Cookin</i> with Miles Davis <i>Miles Ahead</i> with Miles Davis <i>Gil Evans & Ten</i> with Gil Evans <i>Curtis Fuller with Red Garland</i> with Curtis Fuller <i>The Opener</i> with Curtis Fuller <i>Bone & Bari</i> with Curtis Fuller <i>Red Garland's Piano</i> with Red Garland <i>Groovy</i> with Red Garland <i>The P.C. Blues</i> with Red Garland <i>Benny Golson's New York Scene</i> with Benny Golson <i>A Blowin' Session</i> with Johnny Griffin <i>The Congregation</i> with Johnny Griffin <i>First Place</i> with J. J. Johnson <i>That's Him!</i> with Abbey Lincoln <i>Lee Morgan Vol. 3</i> with Lee Morgan <i>City Lights</i> with Lee Morgan <i>The Cooker</i> with Lee Morgan <i>Sonny Rollins, Vol. 2</i> with Sonny Rollins <i>The Sound of Sonny</i> with Sonny Rollins
1958	<i>Kenny Burrell & John Coltrane</i> with Kenny Burrell <i>Cool Struttin'</i> with Sonny Clark <i>Blues in the Night</i> with Sonny Clark <i>Blue Train</i> with John Coltrane <i>Bahia</i> with John Coltrane <i>Black Pearls</i> with John Coltrane

Table 2.2 Paul Chambers' Discography (cont.)

Period	Album/Artist
1958	<i>Settin' the Pace</i> John Coltrane with the Red Garland Trio with John Coltrane <i>Soultrane</i> with John Coltrane <i>Stardust</i> with John Coltrane <i>The Believer</i> with John Coltrane <i>The Last Trane</i> with John Coltrane <i>Relaxin'</i> with Miles Davis <i>1958 Miles</i> with Miles Davis <i>Milestones</i> with Miles Davis <i>Jazz at the Plaza Vol. I</i> with Miles Davis <i>New Bottle Old Wine</i> with Gil Evans <i>Dig It!</i> with Red Garland <i>Can't See for Lookin'</i> with Red Garland <i>It's a Blue World</i> with Red Garland <i>Manteca</i> with Red Garland <i>The Modern Touch</i> with Benny Golson <i>Bennie Green Blows His Horn</i> with Bennie Green <i>Piano</i> with Wynton Kelly <i>It's Magic</i> with Abbey Lincoln
1959	<i>Just Friends</i> with Julian "Cannonball" Adderley <i>Cannonball Adderley Quintet in Chicago</i> with Julian "Cannonball" Adderley <i>Cannonball Takes Charge</i> with Julian "Cannonball" Adderley <i>Chet Baker in New York</i> with Chet Baker <i>Chet</i> with Chet Baker <i>My Conception</i> with Sonny Clark <i>Porgy and Bess</i> with Miles Davis <i>Kind of Blue</i> with Miles Davis <i>Blue Spring</i> with Kenny Dorham

Table 2.2 Paul Chambers' Discography (cont.)

Period	Album/Artist
1959	<i>Quiet Kenny</i> with Kenny Dorham <i>Sliding Easy</i> with Curtis Fuller <i>The Curtis Fuller Jazztet</i> with Curtis Fuller <i>All Kinds of Weather</i> with Red Garland <i>Red in Blues-ville</i> with Red Garland <i>Groovin' with Golson</i> with Benny Golson <i>The Thumper</i> with Jimmy Heath <i>Bags' Opus</i> with Milt Jackson <i>Kelly Blue</i> with Wynton Kelly
1960	<i>Motor City Scene</i> with Donald Byrd <i>Bags & Trane</i> with John Coltrane <i>Giant Steps</i> with John Coltrane <i>Steamin'</i> with Miles Davis <i>Sketches of Spain</i> with Miles Davis <i>The Red Garland Trio</i> with Red Garland <i>Bags & Trane</i> with Milt Jackson <i>The Great Kai & J. J.</i> with J. J. Johnson <i>Philly Joe's Beat</i> with Philly Joe Jones <i>Kelly at Midnight</i> with Wynton Kelly <i>Kelly Great</i> with Wynton Kelly <i>The New Scene of King Curtis</i> with King Curtis <i>Soul Meeting</i> with King Curtis <i>Lee-Way</i> with Lee Morgan <i>Here's Lee Morgan</i> with Lee Morgan

Table 2.2 Paul Chambers' Discography (cont.)

Period	Album/Artist
1961	<i>Naturally!</i> with Nat Adderley <i>Lush Life</i> with John Coltrane <i>Workin' </i> with Miles Davis <i>Someday My Prince Will Come</i> with Miles Davis <i>In Person Friday and Saturday Nights at the Blackhawk, Complete</i> with Miles Davis <i>Whistle Stop</i> with Kenny Dorham <i>Pop + Jazz = Swing</i> with Benny Golson <i>Dexter Calling...</i> with Dexter Gordon <i>Landslide</i> with Dexter Gordon <i>Glidin' Along</i> with Bennie Green <i>Here's Hope!</i> with Elmo Hope <i>High Hope!</i> with Elmo Hope <i>Statements</i> with Milt Jackson <i>Together!</i> with Philly Joe Jones <i>Wynton Kelly!</i> with Wynton Kelly
1962	<i>Quiet Nights</i> with Miles Davis <i>Turning Point</i> with Benny Golson
1963	<i>Comin' in the Back Door</i> with Wynton Kelly <i>Soul Hits</i> with Les McCann <i>A Bag of Gold</i> with Les McCann
1964	<i>Toshiko Mariano and her Big Band</i> with Toshiko Akiyoshi <i>The Individualism of Gil Evans</i> with Gil Evans <i>On the Trail</i> with Jimmy Heath <i>It's All Right!</i> with Wynton Kelly
1965	<i>Undiluted</i> with Wynton Kelly <i>Blues on Purpose</i> with Wynton Kelly

Table 2.2 Paul Chambers' Discography (cont.)

Period	Album/Artist
1966	<i>This Is Criss!</i> with Sonny Criss <i>Charisma</i> with Lee Morgan <i>The Rajah</i> with Lee Morgan
1967	<i>Portrait of Sonny Criss</i> with Sonny Criss
1968	<i>Four</i> with Joe Henderson <i>Straight, No Chaser</i> with Joe Henderson <i>Last Trio Session</i> with Wynton Kelly
1969	<i>Red Garland Revisited!</i> with Red Garland
2015	<i>Miles Davis at Newport 1955-1975: The Bootleg Series Vol. 4</i>

2.2.3 Biography of Jimmy Garrison

Jimmy Garrison, a luminary in the pantheon of jazz bassists, was born on March 3, 1934, in Miami, Florida. His formative years were shaped by a move to Philadelphia at the age of ten—a city steeped in a rich musical heritage that would prove instrumental in Garrison's development as a musician. It wasn't until his senior year of high school that he chose the bass, a decision that would set him on the path to jazz greatness (allaboutjazz.com, 2015).

In the Philadelphia jazz scene of 1957, Garrison's burgeoning talent facilitated a brief yet significant collaboration with the now-iconic John Coltrane and pianist McCoy Tyner. This early encounter foreshadowed a deeper, more lasting alliance that would emerge later in his career. The following year, Garrison relocated to the jazz nexus of New York City, where his talents flourished alongside jazz greats such as Philly Joe Jones, Kenny Dorham, and Tony Scott. It was also in 1958 that he made his recording debut on the album *Blues for Dracula*, heralding the beginning of an impressive discography (Combs, 2018, p. 1).

1959 also marked a turning point in Garrison's career when he joined forces with avant-garde saxophonist Ornette Coleman on *Art of the Improvisers*, a collaboration that would bolster his standing in the competitive New York jazz milieu and earn him critical acclaim.

In 1961, Garrison's musical journey took a definitive turn when he became a vital member of the John Coltrane Quartet, contributing to the groundbreaking album *My Favorite Things*. Garrison's rich, resonant bass line became a cornerstone of the quartet's innovative sound, which pushed jazz into uncharted territories. Alongside McCoy Tyner and Elvin Jones, Garrison helped forge a new jazz language that continues to influence the genre (allaboutjazz.com, 2017).

After the untimely death of John Coltrane in 1967, Garrison's artistry remained in high demand. He revisited his collaborative roots with Ornette Coleman and explored new musical landscapes with Alice Coltrane. Additionally, Garrison's passion for education led him to impart his extensive knowledge to the next generation of musicians at Bennington and Wesleyan colleges, with Willam Park standing out among his many accomplished students.

Tragically, Jimmy Garrison's life was brought to an abrupt end on April 7, 1976, in New York City due to lung cancer. His premature departure from the jazz world left a void, but his profound influence can still be felt. Garrison's legacy lives on through his innovative recordings and his dedicated mentorship, which continues to inspire bass players and jazz enthusiasts alike. His contributions to the language of jazz, particularly within the context of the Coltrane Quartet, solidify his status as one of the genre's most revered bassists (Chris, 2012).

2.2.4 Discography

Table 2.3 Jimmy Garrisons' Discography

Period	Album/Artist
1958	<i>Blues for Dracula</i> with Philly Joe Jones
1959	<i>Blues-ette</i> with Curtis Fuller <i>Imagination</i> with Curtis Fuller <i>Drums Around the World</i> with Philly Joe Jones <i>Showcase</i> with Philly Joe Jones <i>Live at the Half Note</i> with Lee Konitz <i>Swing, Swang, Swingin'</i> with Jackie McLean <i>Straight Ahead</i> with J. R. Monterose <i>Golden Moments</i> with Tony Scott <i>I'll Remember</i> with Tony Scott <i>Art of the Improvisers</i> with Ornette Coleman
1960	<i>Jazz Contemporary</i> with Kenny Dorham <i>Showboat</i> with Kenny Dorham <i>Images of Curtis Fuller</i> with Curtis Fuller
1961	<i>The Tenor Stylings of Bill Barron</i> with Bill Barron <i>Speak Low</i> with Walter Bishop Jr. <i>Further Definitions</i> with Benny Carter <i>Ornette on Tenor</i> with Ornette Coleman <i>Live at the Village Vanguard</i> with John Coltrane <i>Plenty of Horn</i> with Ted Curson <i>The Magnificent Trombone of Curtis Fuller</i> with Curtis Fuller <i>Blues to Coltrane</i> with Cal Massey <i>My favorite things</i> with John Coltrane
1962	<i>Ballads</i> with John Coltrane <i>Duke Ellington & John Coltrane</i> with John Coltrane

Table 2.3 Jimmy Garrisons' Discography (cont.)

Period	Album/Artist
1963	<i>Illumination!</i> with Elvin Jones <i>For Swingers Only</i> with Lorez Alexandria <i>John Coltrane and Johnny Hartman</i> with John Coltrane <i>Impressions</i> with John Coltrane <i>Live at Birdland</i> with John Coltrane <i>Today and Tomorrow</i> with McCoy Tyner
1964	<i>Crescent</i> with John Coltrane <i>A Love Supreme</i> with John Coltrane <i>McCoy Tyner Plays Ellington</i> with McCoy Tyner
1965	<i>Ascension</i> with John Coltrane <i>First Meditations</i> with John Coltrane <i>The John Coltrane Quartet Plays</i> with John Coltrane <i>Kulu Sé Mama</i> with John Coltrane <i>The New Wave in Jazz</i> with John Coltrane <i>Live at the Half Note: One Down, One Up</i> with John Coltrane <i>Live in Seattle</i> with John Coltrane <i>The Major Works of John Coltrane</i> with John Coltrane <i>Meditations</i> with John Coltrane <i>Transition</i> with John Coltrane <i>Sun Ship</i> with John Coltrane <i>Live in Antibes</i> with John Coltrane
1966	<i>Live in Japan</i> with John Coltrane <i>Live at the Village Vanguard Again!</i> with John Coltrane <i>East Broadway Run Down</i> with Sonny Rollins

Table 2.3 Jimmy Garrisons' Discography (cont.)

Period	Album/Artist
1967	<i>Expression</i> with John Coltrane <i>The Olatunji Concert: The Last Live Recording</i> with John Coltrane <i>Stellar Regions</i> with John Coltrane <i>Intents and Purposes</i> with Bill Dixon <i>Impressions of New York</i> with Rolf Kühn and Joachim Kühn <i>Good Golly Miss Nancy</i> with Robert Pozar <i>Life at the Donaueschingen Music Festival</i> with Archie Shepp <i>Freedom & Unity</i> with Clifford Thornton
1968	<i>New York Is Now!</i> with Ornette Coleman <i>Love Call</i> with Ornette Coleman <i>A Monastic Trio</i> with Alice Coltrane <i>Cosmic Music</i> with Alice Coltrane <i>Puttin' It Together</i> with Elvin Jones <i>The Ultimate</i> with Elvin Jones
1969	<i>Rules of Freedom</i> with Nathan Davis
1970	<i>The Art of the Improvisers</i> with Ornette Coleman
1971	<i>Universal Consciousness</i> with Alice Coltrane
1972	<i>Attica Blues</i> with Archie Shepp <i>The Cry of My People</i> with Archie Shepp
1975	<i>From Ragtime to No Time</i> with Beaver Harris <i>There's a Trumpet in My Soul</i> with Archie Shepp

2.2.5 Biography of Christian McBride

Christian McBride was born on May 21, 1972, in Philadelphia. Living in a musical family, McBride started playing electric bass at eight, eventually moving on to upright bass. In 1987, he enrolled at Philadelphia's High School for the Performing Arts, where he studied classical bass under Neil Courtney of the Philadelphia Orchestra, funding his purchase of an upright bass through the Philadelphia Music Awards. During high school, McBride was invited by Wynton Marsalis with Marsalis' band at the

Academy of Music in Philadelphia, then performed in Germany with the Philadelphia Youth Orchestra for two weeks. In 1989, McBride won scholarships in the Finals of Musicfest U.S.A. and was chosen an All-Star in the stage band and jazz combo categories; in the same year, McBride came to Juilliard School of Music with a scholarship.

While attending Juilliard, McBride, at a mere 17, was invited by Bobby Watson to join his band Horizon. “Talk about being thrown into the pit: it was Boddy Watson, James Williams, and Victor Lweis, and it was like an iron brand going into me” (Collar, 2024). In the subsequent years, McBride gained significant experience by cooperating with artists like Bobby Watson, Freddie Hubbard, Benny Golson, George Duke, Milt Jackson, J. J. Johnson, and Hank Jones, along with contemporaries such as Roy Hargrove, Benny Green, and Joshua Redman. In 1996, jazz bassist Ray Brown created a group named SuperBass alongside McBride and John Clayton. Two albums had released by the group and named: *SuperBass: Live at Scullers* (1997) and *SuperBass 2: Live at the Blue Note* (2001). Later that same year, McBride recorded the album *Young Lions and Old Tigers* with Dave Brubeck (christianmcbride.com, 2020).

In the 21st century, from 2000 to 2008, McBride led his own band—the Christian McBride Band—and released two albums, *Vertical Vision* (2003) and *Live at Tonic* (2006). In 2011, McBride launched his debut big band album, *The Good Feeling*, winning the Grammy for Best Large Jazz Ensemble Performance. In the past thirty years, McBride has had many achievements, including leading many jazz bands, hosting music radio, and being an eight-time Grammy Award winner. McBride, as a sideman, has recorded over 300 albums since 1989. No doubt he is an iconic jazz musician already (Scott, 2011).

2.2.6 Discography

Table 2.4 Christian McBrides' Discography

Period	Album/Artist
1994	<i>Gettin' to It</i>
1995	<i>Number Two Express</i>
1998	<i>A Family Affair</i>
2000	<i>SciFi</i>
2000	<i>The Philadelphia Experiment</i>
2002	<i>Vertical Vision</i>
2005	<i>Live at Tonic</i>
2009	<i>Kind of Brown</i>
2011	<i>The Good Feeling</i>
2011	<i>Conversations with Christian</i>
2013	<i>Out Here</i> <i>People Music</i>
2015	<i>Live at the Village Vanguard</i>
2017	<i>Bringin' It</i>
2018	<i>Christian McBride's New Jawn</i>
2020	<i>The Movement Revisited</i> <i>For Jimmy, Wes and Oliver</i>
2021	<i>Live at the Village Vanguard</i>
2023	<i>Prime</i>
2024	<i>But Who's Gonna Play the Melody?</i>

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology employed in this paper primarily encompasses three approaches, namely data collection from diverse sources, subsequent transcription, and, ultimately, analysis to derive conclusions. The initial section will describe the process of obtaining scores and the channels through which they were acquired. The subsequent segment will discuss the transcription method along with practical considerations. Lastly, the third part will expound upon the analysis techniques and methodologies used throughout this study.

3.1 Data Collection

Since most songs featured in the author's concert are jazz standards, *The Real Books* will serve as the primary source for lead sheets. In my recital, "Dear Old Stockholm," and "Soul Eyes," are sourced from *Real Books*. However, certain songs cannot be found within these resources; for instance, the lead sheet of "Resolution" required me to utilize an online platform ([musescore.com](https://www.musescore.com)) and consult research papers with similar content. For music scores lacking resources of lead sheets like "My Favorite Things" by Christian McBride, the author searched for relevant performance videos to transcribe himself.

3.2 Transcription

In preparation for the concert, due to a scarcity of musical score resources, the author primarily transcribed Christian McBride's rendition of "My Favorite Things." Given the intricacy of the original recording, the author commenced by studying videos of other ensembles performing this piece. After meticulously comparing multiple versions in both audio and video formats, it was observed that the cover version

exhibited a more succinct rhythm and harmony while maintaining an overall framework that slightly deviated from the original rendition but did not compromise its performance impact. Consequently, it proved more feasible to transcribe. Over two weeks, Christian McBride's interpretation of "My Favorite Things" underwent meticulous refinement. In comparison with other songs analyzed during this process, the transcription part includes the solo of "Dear Old Stockholm", the bass line of "Soul Eyes," and the bass line of "A Love Supreme Part II: Resolution". Throughout this endeavor, Riffstation (transcription software) was predominantly utilized by the author to painstakingly capture each section of sheet music with utmost precision in order to restore every intricate detail. Simultaneously, as these scores were being captured, significant enhancements were made in intonation accuracy, timbre quality, and rhythmic proficiency.

3.3 Analysis

For the analysis section, providing more detailed and professional descriptions is vital. In this regard, reference will be made to authoritative sources such as *Concepts for Bass Soloing* by Chuck Sher and Marc Johnson and *The Jazz Bass Line Book* by Mike Downes. Moreover, relevant analytical terminology, including, but not limited to, a comprehensive examination of rhythm, scale variations, and walking lines, will be conducted to objectively portray the performance characteristics of jazz double bass across different periods. In addition, some musical terminology will use in a description of music, including Skip, Sequence, Chromatic approach, Double stops, Root emphasizes, Grace note, Passing tone(pt.), Riff, Pedal, Unison, Octave, Groove, Counterpoint, Enclosure.

3.4 Application to practice

After all transcription and analysis, the final goal was to re-perform the bass line and solo of the four songs by using the skills acquired from the styles of the three bassists. This will enable the author to put his newfound skills into practice. In the

process of practice, the author will not only learn from and integrate the styles of the three bass players but also use certain scales and rhythms to highlight the stylistic characteristics of each song to achieve the purpose of playing a more personal style.

CHAPTER IV

ANALYSIS OF PAUL CHAMBERS, JIMMY GARRISON, AND CHRISTIAN MCBRIDE

4.1 Analysis of Paul Chambers's style in "Dear Old Stockholm"

For the author's recital, one of Paul Chambers's most famous tunes, "Dear Old Stockholm," was chosen. This folk song from Sweden was performed by many jazz masters, including Miles Davis, John Coltrane, Red Garland, and, of course, Paul Chambers. John Coltrane, in particular, recorded this song many times over several years, and this remarkable version was played with drummer Roy Haynes.

4.1.1 Introduction to "Dear Old Stockholm"

In 1957, Paul Chambers, as a lead man, released the Blue Note album *Bass on Top*, which included "Dear Old Stockholm." The side players included Kenny Burrell on guitar, Hank Jones on piano, and Art Taylor on drums. This tune has a unique form. Jazz standards often have forms of 12 or 32 bars, but this AABC tune has one A section of 24 bars, a B section of 4 bars, and a C section of 15 bars for a total of 43 bars.

4.1.2 Analysis of "Dear Old Stockholm" Bass Solo

In mm.1-8, Chambers employs the chromatic approach by playing F, E, and Eb as a transition to the root note in the subsequent measure under the Dm chord. Building upon this Dm chord foundation, Chambers proceeds to execute an arpeggio within the framework of the D Dorian mode. Most impressive is Chambers's seamless transformation from the Dorian mode to the D harmonic minor scale in m. 3, with C# serving as a distinctive tonal element. Employing a scale during this transition allows Chambers to showcase his solo prowess over two bars on a single chord. Following several notes from the Dorian mode, a new chorus commences.

Chambers commences the solo, employing the A Phrygian mode as a recurring motif. He then transitions to the F Ionian mode, followed by incorporating the

Gm7 arpeggio no root but with a tension note 9th (natural A). In m. 7, he briefly uses a chromatic approach from Eb to natural E in his solo. Returning to the D harmonic minor scale, he maintains this melodic pattern until m. 9.

Figure 4.1 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 1–8.

In m. 10, Chambers introduces the arpeggio of chord tones in Em7 as a recurring motif, followed by the continuation of the A7 arpeggio starting on its 3rd note and incorporating Bb as the 9th note. This creates a more “bebop” bass line. What sets this measure apart is Chambers's use of triplets consisting of eighth and quarter notes, creating a sharp contrast that enhances the dynamic quality of the melody. Particularly noteworthy is how this eighth-note triplet seamlessly connects with the dotted quarter notes in m.12, resulting in an increased sense of swing feel. Furthermore, Chambers maintains this rhythmic pattern in mm.12 and 13. Subsequently, he transitions to the Dorian mode, utilizing arpeggios based on Dm7 chord tones and employing syncopation again in m.14.

Figure 4.2 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 9–16.

In m.17, Chambers employs the Dorian mode as the motif and subsequently transitions from the 5th to the root of an A Phrygian mode in m.18. The eighth note pause enhances rhythmic dynamism, leading to a shift to the F Ionian mode in m. 19. In m. 20, Chambers skillfully utilize enclosure around natural B to establish an unconventional interval and promptly switches to the D harmonic minor scale. In m. 22, Chambers showcases his utilization of a distinctive Eb whole-tone scale, with Bb as a passing note. This choice creates an audibly distinct sound due to the employment of the Eb whole-tone scale before transitioning smoothly into the A Locrian mode in m. 23. Mm. 22 and 23 exemplify how Chambers crafts melodies centered around the Eb note while seamlessly transitioning between two different scales—a striking demonstration of his soloing technique. Subsequently, he returns once again to employing the Dorian mode.

Figure 4.3 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 17–24.

From mm.25 to 32, Chambers consistently incorporates the D Aeolian mode and employs it in mm. 26 to 27, integrating quarter-note rests and eighth-note rests to enhance rhythmic dynamism. Notably, Chambers executes a smooth transition between the F Ionian mode and the D minor scale from mm. 28 to 32, employing three different modes and scales such as F Ionian mode, D harmonic minor scale, and Dorian mode, depending on the chord changes. In m. 31, a descending arpeggio commences on Bb and resolves on C#, from the triad arpeggio of E halfdim7 move to the 3rd note of A7; deliberately avoiding resolution on the root creates a sense of incompleteness while generating an exhilarating auditory effect.

25 Dm⁶ Dm⁷ Dm⁶ Fmaj⁷
Aeolian mode

29 Gm⁷ C⁷ Fmaj⁷ E^{ø7} arpeggio A⁷ Dm
Ionian mode Harmonic minor scale Dorian mode

Figure 4.4 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 25–32.

In m. 34, the phrase commences on an upbeat, followed by triplet eighth notes. Subsequently, a series of arpeggios under the Ionian mode are introduced, incorporating the chord tones of C⁹ and Dm⁷. The progression smoothly transitions between these two chords using the 9th pitch of C⁷ and the 7th pitch of Dm⁷. Following this passage, Chambers shifts to the bridge in D Aeolian before employing the C Mixolydian mode for the rest of the section. The section begins with syncopation featuring an eighth-note rest, while throughout this segment, Chambers consistently incorporates B as a passing note to establish dominance within bebop scales in m. 40.

33 E^{ø7} A⁷ Gm⁷ C⁷ arpeggio Fmaj⁷ E^{ø7} A⁷
3 Ionian mode Aeolian mode

37 Dm C⁷(sus4)
Mixolydian mode

Figure 4.5 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 33–40.

After mm. 38 to 44, which concludes one chorus, Chambers introduces a bridge in m. 45, where he skillfully executes the sequence of the D Aeolian mode with precision and regularity. Subsequently, he strategically incorporates quarter-note and eighth-note rests to enhance rhythmic dynamics and transitions into the upcoming chorus.

Figure 4.6 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 41–48.

In m. 49, Chambers plays a Bb major 7th arpeggio and employs Bb as a connecting note to transition into an inverted Dm arpeggio, Subsequently, he skillfully incorporates skips to articulate the chord tones of E half diminished 7 and A7 before transitioning into the D Dorian mode. In m. 51, he utilizes eighth-note rests to enhance rhythmic dynamism. In m. 53, Chambers explores the E Locrian mode while incorporating an enclosure around B. Furthermore, in m. 54, he seamlessly connects notes D and A by employing one passing note, the natural C. Following this progression, Chambers proceeds with an ascending sequence in D Aeolian, culminating in higher pitches.

Figure 4.7 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 49–56.

In mm. 57 and 58, Chambers plays a short sequence incorporating staccato eighth notes to introduce rhythmic variation and resolves on A. Following a brief pause, from mm. 59 to 62, Chambers proceeds with the harmonic minor scale while consistently initiating each phrase on C# and E. In measures 63 to 64, there is a transition

to the harmonic minor scale accompanied by a triplet quarter note pattern that enhances the rhythmic dynamism.

Figure 4.8 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 57–64.

During this section, Chambers incorporates the Phrygian modes on E and A from m. 65 to m. 66, followed by syncopated chord tones of Dm7. After a brief pause, in m. 69, Chambers executes a gradual descent in the Dm chord, transitioning smoothly from D to A. Chambers maintains rhythmic symmetry throughout this descending passage to infuse the melody. The phrase is concluded on a high pitch of Fmaj7 in F, then goes down to C and ingeniously combines an eighth-note chromatic approach to arpeggio in m. 72 and form a Dm arpeggio 7th under C7, resulting in a crafted musical phrase.

Figure 4.9 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 65–72.

M. 73 follows the progression of m. 72, where the melody transitions to the F Ionian mode. In m. 75, Chambers introduces the Aeolian mode on D as a motif before transitioning to Gm7 and C7 chord tones. Within C7, Chambers omits the root and smoothly incorporates the tension note D using an arpeggio, which resolves to the fifth note of Fmaj7 and returns to F Ionian mode. A new phrase is initiated in m. 78 with an

upbeat on Eb using a chromatic approach, followed by E half diminished 7th and A7 chord tones without their roots to connect with the A note in the next measure, subsequently initiating a walking bass line. Utilizing arpeggios from the 3rd through the 9th provides a transition between consecutive chord tones.

73 Fmaj7 Eø7 A7 Dm Eø7 A7
 Ionian mode Aeolian mode

77 Gm7 C7 Fmaj7 Eø7 A7 Dm
 chord tone arpeggio Ionian mode chromatic approach arpeggio

Figure 4.10 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 73–80.

In the final section of the solo, Chambers adeptly employs the C Mixolydian mode beneath the C7 chord, incorporating a recurring motif centered around the root note. From mm. 81 to 86, he artfully utilizes arpeggios and melodic repetition before transitioning to the harmonic minor scale in m. 87, ultimately concluding with a resolution on the D root note.

81 C7(sus4)
 Mixolydian mode

85 C7(sus4) A7 Dm
 Mixolydian mode

Figure 4.11 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 81–88.

4.2 Analysis of Jimmy Garrison’s Bass Line in “Soul Eyes”

4.2.1 Introduction to “Soul Eyes”

This composition, featuring lyrics by Mal Waldron, is a 32-bar ABAC form (four eight-bar sections) in 4/4 time in a ballad style. In 1962, John Coltrane recorded the song on his album *Coltrane*, marking his second rendition of this piece. Subsequently, “Soul Eyes” became a jazz standard and was recorded by various musicians.

4.2.2 Analysis of “Soul Eyes” Bass Lines

In this tune, Coltrane’s quartet recorded three choruses in total. In the beginning, from mm. 1 to 8, we see that Garrison uses a pattern based on two half notes for each measure where the second half note is replaced by a quarter note tied to a triplet. Garrison mostly uses the root and fifth notes, but the interesting thing is what he plays in the triplet passing tone, such as in m. 4, when the C leaps to Eb, then chromatically to F via the passing tone E. Mm. 2 through 5 comp the same way. This is a smooth way to embellish forms by chromaticism; there is a feeling of space while the rhythm becomes more active.

The musical notation shows the bass line for measures 1-8 of "Soul Eyes". It is written in bass clef with a key signature of two flats (Bb and Eb) and a common time signature (C). The first staff contains measures 1-4, and the second staff contains measures 5-8. Chord symbols are placed above the notes: Cm7 (measures 1, 4), G7(b9) (measure 2), F7(#11) (measure 6), Fm7 (measure 5), Bb7(alt) (measure 5), Gm7(b5) (measure 7), and C7(b9) (measure 8). Annotations include "Chromatic approach" and "Pt" (passing tone) for the triplet notes in measures 4, 5, 6, and 7. Rhythmic markings include "R" for root, "5th" for fifth, and "3" for triplet.

Figure 4.12 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 1–8.

In the B part, Garrison uses a more syncopated rhythm still based on triplets, but further subdividing them by adding sixteenth notes, connecting with a quarter note in m.10 and m.14. In m.14, he plays an A natural in Bb7—the so-called bebop note

(raised 7th)—giving the bass line a more ‘bop’ feel. Garrison also uses triplet sixteenth notes in m. 16. Garrison uses chord tones like the root, 5th, and b5th.

Figure 4.13 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 9–16.

Back to the A section, Garrison continues to use half notes and quarter notes with triplet eighth notes. He uses the chromatic approach from m. 18 to m. 22 to build the bass line, as it is a very effective way to get from one chord tone to another. A particularly interesting part is in m. 22, where Garrison uses an arpeggio with triplets around the root, 3rd, and 5th to give the bass line more of a feel of space and a definitive change of chord. In m. 23, Garrison uses a Chromatic approach from D to C.

Figure 4.14 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 17–24.

In the C section, Garrison creates bass lines with more arpeggios after a chromatic approach in m. 27, following a beautiful arpeggio based on a C triad in triplets in m. 28. In m. 29, Garrison also uses arpeggio with sixteenth notes, providing yet another rhythmic variation, and, in m.30, the 4th and 5th notes above the root to complete an arpeggio of B♭ triad with inverted.

Figure 4.15 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 25–32.

After the head in, the bass plays in walking style in m. 33. A featured note for the C Dorian mode is A natural, which builds a dissonant interval with the preceding Eb, creating tension. In m. 35, Garrison continues to use triads to build arpeggios, and in m. 36, he uses double stops of root and 5th to create a harmonious sound. After a chromatic approach in m. 37, and, in m. 39, he then plays repeated root notes in m. 39 make interesting rhythms, with D as a skip note. In m. 40, he plays a C arpeggio, briefly adding Db to suggest the C7b9 chord.

Figure 4.16 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 33–40.

Later on, Garrison focuses on the root note in m. 41 and m. 45, both of which use the same rhythm and ornament the root with the third or 5th, giving the bass a distinct groove. In mm. 47 and 48, Garrison uses the Ionian and Mixolydian modes. For this part, Garrison plays a more complex rhythm with many sixteenth notes, mostly reflecting the chromatic approach, and the ties make the sixteenth notes more energetic.

Figure 4.17 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 41–48.

For mm.49 to 56, Garrison uses a chord tone arpeggio in m. 49, emphasizing the 5th. In m. 50, Garrison plays a wide jump from D to G, with D as a skip note for the root. The wide jump is another technique to make the bass line more dynamic. In m. 52, Garrison uses the F mixolydian mode to build the bass line, and in m. 54, the F# note acts as a featured note, revealing the altered scale of Bb with F natural as a passing tone connected to the next bar. In m. 55, G has a jump go down to Bb then skip to A natural.

Figure 4.18 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 49–56.

In m. 57, Garrison inserts a non-scale tone B in Ab Ionian mode. In m. 58, the bass part focuses on the root note D, with Garrison using an octave and D triad to emphasize the D note. In m. 59, the Bb and B yield an altered G scale, and, in m.60, the arpeggio of C7b5 not only includes chord tones but also has tension notes of D and passing tone of Db descending to root C, making the bass line sound more excited. After a chromatic approach from F to Bb in mm. 61 to 62, in m. 62, Garrison uses the 4ths interval and arpeggio to build the bass line, and a tie connects two Bb notes, creating a delayed feel, as in m. 63, which also uses triad arpeggiation.

Figure 4.19 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 57–64.

In m. 65, Garrison plays an arpeggio in many sixteenth notes, with D as a tension note under Cm7. Noteworthy in m. 66 is Garrison’s use of octave and 5th double stops to improve the harmony, while two ties make the rhythm more dynamic after the double stops. Garrison plays in a high position and then jumps to a low position, making the bass line more exciting and unpredictable. In m. 67, the rhythm becomes more complex as Garrison uses a chromatic approach in a sixteenth note and continues to use syncopation to play triadic notes, emphasizing Eb. Meanwhile, Garrison again uses ties to give the rhythm a more laid-back feel. In m. 68, Garrison uses the F Mixolydian mode to build the bass line and connects to m. 69, where a syncopated ascending F Aeolian mode under Fm7 ends at a B natural passing tone and moves to Bb. In m. 70, F# acts as a featured note in the Bb altered scale. In m.72, Garrison plays the C Mixolydian mode over the whole measure, emphasizing G.

Figure 4.20 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 65–72.

In m. 73, Garrison plays the root, 9th, 3rd, 5th, and 7th of the Ab Ionian mode. In m. 74, the Eb notes of the Locrian mode are conspicuous. In m.76, an arpeggiated triad is used again, from Db up to Bb, then back to Db. Meanwhile, the 4th

as passing tones and 13th notes are neighboring tones connecting each chord tone, as in m. 77, where a triad under Gbmaj7 is used again.

73 $A\flat\text{maj}7$ $A\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $D7(\text{b}9)$ $G\text{maj}7$ $D\flat7$

77 $G\flat\text{maj}7$ $F\text{m}7$ $B\flat7$ $E\flat\text{maj}7$ $D\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $G7(\text{b}9)$ $\text{b}5$

Annotations: Ionian mode, Locrian mode, arpeggio.

Figure 4.21 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 73–80.

The bass line returns to a two-feel for mm. 81 to 88, back to the theme and double-time finish. In m. 82, Garrison uses the chromatic approach in sixteenth-notes triplets while using the chromatic approach in sixteenth-notes in m. 85. A Bb7 arpeggio in m. 86 again features the altered scale pitch of F#, which is a striking choice for the arpeggio. After a chromatic approach by triplet in m. 87, the triadic arpeggio continues under C7.

81 $C\text{m}7$ $G7(\text{b}9)$ $C\text{m}7$ $F7(\#\text{11})$

85 $F\text{m}7$ $B\flat7\text{alt.}$ $G\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $C7(\text{b}9)$

Annotations: Chromatic approach, arpeggio.

Figure 4.22 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 81–88.

In the last part of the C section, the Eb is a common note in m. 89 and m. 90 are emphasized through a dynamic rhythm, and, in mm. 91 to 92, Garrison uses a chromatic approach from C to G. After the chromatic approach to Fm7, Garrison uses a bow to play the roots of Ebmaj7 and Bmaj13, providing a wonderful ending.

Figure 4.23 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 89–97.

4.2.3 Introduction to *A Love Supreme* “Part II: Resolution”

The track “Resolution” is from the album *A Love Supreme*, widely acclaimed as one of the most significant jazz albums in history, owing to its groundbreaking musical innovations, profound spiritual depth, and immense influence on the genre. Released in 1965 and featuring John Coltrane, McCoy Tyner, Jimmy Garrison, and Elvin Jones, this masterpiece unequivocally showcases Coltrane's invaluable contributions to the realm of jazz.

4.2.4 Analysis of *A Love Supreme* “Part II: Resolutions” Bass lines

The composition commences with a bass solo, showcasing Jimmy Garrison's adept utilization of double stop technique employing intervals of fourths. The melodic movement is rooted in the Eb Dorian mode, while Garrison employs regular rhythmic patterns to construct a harmonically rich melody, imbuing the entire introduction with distinctive features in both rhythm and melody. Throughout the intro, Garrison incorporates quintuplets to enhance rhythmic flexibility. Starting from m. 13, the interval of the fourth harmonic progression ascends continuously until reaching its climax at C and F before seamlessly transitioning into the theme accompanied by snare drum accents. Due to its unique structure and design, this introduction has become an iconic hallmark of the jazz bass line.

The musical score is written in bass clef with a key signature of three flats (Eb major) and a common time signature. It consists of four staves of music. The first staff is labeled 'bass intro' and 'Eb m' with 'double stops' written above it. The second staff is labeled '5' and 'Riff on Eb m dorian mode'. The third staff is labeled '9'. The fourth staff is labeled '13'. The music features various rhythmic patterns, including dotted quarter notes, eighth notes, and double stops.

Figure 4.24 “Resolution,” mm. 1–16.

Regarding the head section, Garrison's approach in Eb centers around accentuating the dotted quarter note and utilizing it as a recurring motif, which undergoes certain variations. In addition, Garrison incorporates rhythmic elements such as syncopated half notes, double stops, and triplet quarter and eighth notes. In terms of note selection, Garrison predominantly focuses on the root and 5th notes while employing diverse rhythms to ensure compatibility with other instruments.

17 Ebm^{9/6} sax melody R 5th B⁷(sus4)

21 F⁷(^{#9}/₄₅) Ebm root emphasize B^b7^{alt.}

25 Ebm^{9/6} B⁷(sus4)

29 F⁷(^{#9}/₄₅) F¹³(^{#9}) B^b13(^{b9}) double stops

33 Ebm^{9/6} root emphasize B⁷(sus4) root emphasize double stops 3-3 3-3

37 F⁷(^{#9}) double stops F⁷(^{#5}) E⁶ B^b7 B^b13(^{b9}) double stops

Figure 4.25 “Resolution,” mm. 17–40.

After the head-in, during the bridge section, Garrison executes a walking bass line. Initially emphasizing Eb, he later incorporates a chromatic approach in certain measures. In mm. 45 and 46, Garrison introduces a minor melody before transitioning to a captivating display of musicality from mm. 49 to 56. Employing double stops enhances the overall sound quality, while the incorporation of quarter and eighth note triplets adds rhythmic complexity. Another noteworthy aspect is Garrison's consistent utilization of an eighth note dotted quarter note pattern throughout numerous measures, resulting in heightened dynamic rhythmical expression. It is worth mentioning that this recurring pattern is rooted in the Eb Dorian mode.

2

Figure 4.26 “Resolution,” mm. 41–56.

Upon completion of the bridge section, the recurring theme melody resurfaces during Garrison's intricate rhythm performance, characterized by a profusion of arpeggio triplets and syncopation. These rhythmic patterns predominantly feature the root and 5th notes of Ebm7, with Garrison employing his signature playing style to accentuate the theme melody. Furthermore, he continues to use double stops skillfully, reminiscent of the introduction section, where fourth intervals are frequently utilized.

57 Ebm^{13} $B7(sus4)$
 melody reprise

61 $F7(\sharp 9)$ $Ebm(\sharp 11)$ $Ebm7(add11)$ Ebm^{13} $B7alt.$

65 Ebm^{13} $B7(sus4)$

69 $F7(\sharp 9)$ $Bb(sus4)$

73 Ebm^{13} $B7(sus4)$

77 $F7(\sharp 9)$ $Ebm(\sharp 11)/Bb$ Ebm^{11} Pt

81 Ebm^9 $B7$
 swing
 piano solo
 skip & melody minor

Figure 4.27 “Resolution,” mm. 57–84.

After the theme concludes, McCoy Tyner commences his solo while Garrison resumes walking. Initially, Garrison employs triplet eighth notes to establish a skipping sensation and incorporates an Eb minor melody in the bass line. He introduces sequences within the bass line, exemplified by a jump pattern in mm. 99 and 100. Subsequently, in mm. 109 to 112, amidst a Dorian mode progression, he skillfully employs half-note processes and transitions seamlessly between chord tones.

The musical score for "Resolution" (mm. 85-112) is presented in bass clef with a key signature of three flats. The score is divided into six systems, each with specific annotations:

- System 1 (mm. 85-88):** Chords: F7(#9), Ebm11, Bb(sus4). Annotations: "3" (triplets) under measures 85-86 and 87-88; "sequence" under measure 88.
- System 2 (mm. 89-92):** Chords: Ebm11, B13.
- System 3 (mm. 93-96):** Chords: A13, G13, Dorian mode, Bb7. Annotation: "3" (triplet) under measure 96.
- System 4 (mm. 97-100):** Chords: Ebm11, B13, A13. Annotations: "3" (triplets) under measures 97-98, 99-100, and 101-102.
- System 5 (mm. 101-104):** Chords: F7(#9), #9, Bb9, Bb7alt. Annotations: "3" (triplets) under measures 101-102, 103-104, and 105-106; "minor pentatonic scale" under measure 103; "parttern" under measure 104.
- System 6 (mm. 105-108):** Chords: Ebm9, B13. Annotations: "3" (triplets) under measures 105-106, 107-108, and 109-110.
- System 7 (mm. 109-112):** Chords: A13, G13, Dorian mode, F13, Bb13. Annotation: "chromatic approach" under measure 112.

Figure 4.28 “Resolution,” mm. 85–112.

From mm. 113 to 128, Garrison consistently employs the Dorian mode, incorporating passing tones and walking bass. In m. 125, he skillfully utilizes a sequence to construct the bass line, enhancing its dynamic qualities. Additionally, he strategically incorporates the repetition of certain notes.

113 $E_b m^{11}$

Dorian mode

117

sequence

121 $E_b m^{6/9}$

3

125

sequence

3

Figure 4.29 “Resolution,” mm. 113–128.

From mm. 129 to 156, Garrison incorporates a higher range and employs a chromatic approach. Initially, he starts with triad arpeggios and utilizes chromaticism to ascend smoothly. He then introduces an E_b minor melody to add variation. Notably, m. 140 showcases Garrison's use of the C whole-tone scale, providing a refreshing tonal quality before transitioning into a sequence of quarter-note progressions leading to C. During this segment, Garrison skillfully employs Locrian mode by playing each note twice from mm.147 to 150, effectively emphasizing its unique characteristics. Continuing with sequences, he proceeds with a descending sequence of descending 5ths in mm. 155 to 156 as a continuation toward the next section.

4

129 Ebm¹¹

129 triad arpeggio chromatic approach

133 melody minor scale

137 Ebm whole-tone scale

141 chromatic approach

145 Ebm Locrian mode

149 Ebm⁷ Ebm¹¹

153 Ebm⁷ Ebm¹¹ C#m¹¹ D7(#9) Gm⁹ G7(#9) E¹³ A7(#9) sequence

Figure 4.30 “Resolution,” mm. 129–156.

The uniqueness of this section lies in m. 163, where Garrison skillfully employs an arpeggio to establish a captivating sequence. Notably, the descending movement from Bb to D indicates the utilization of a Bb whole-tone scale from mm. 162 to 166. Furthermore, incorporating two eighth notes alongside a quarter note creates an intriguing pattern from mm. 162 to 164, with the quarter note as the guide tone from Ab going down to D using a whole-tone scale and in m. 165, B natural as a neighbor tone for Bb. Following the delicate bass line, Garrison proceeds with the Dorian mode.

157 Eb⁹(#5)

161 Ebm⁹

165 neighbor tone

169 Ebm⁹

3

sequence & arpeggio

whole-tone scale

Dorian mode

3

3

Figure 4.31 “Resolution,” mm. 157–172.

At m. 173, Garrison employs the technique of using a chromatic approach with tied notes to create a pattern that effectively produces a delay effect. At m. 177, John Coltrane commences his solo, and Garrison incorporates double stops while utilizing the minor pentatonic scale, all while still emphasizing Eb. In m. 189, Garrison once again utilizes triplets with eighth note triplet arpeggio to create a pattern with various rhythms. Following this section in m.193, he continues playing under the Eb Dorian mode using the walking bass chromatic approach process.

The musical score consists of six staves of bass clef notation in 4/4 time, with a key signature of three flats (B-flat major/C minor). The measures are numbered 173, 177, 181, 185, 189, and 193. Annotations include:
 - Measure 173: 'chromatic approach' and 'B13' (with a '5' above the staff).
 - Measure 177: 'double stops' and 'Eb6/9'.
 - Measure 181: 'F7alt.', 'chromatic approach', 'Eb11', and 'B7(#11)'.
 - Measure 185: 'Eb6/9' and 'minor pentatonic scale'.
 - Measure 189: 'arpeggio' (twice) and 'B7(#11)'.
 - Measure 193: 'Eb6/9' and 'Dorian mode & chromatic approach'.
 The notation includes various intervals, triplets, and chromatic lines.

Figure 4.32 “Resolution,” mm. 173–196.

In m. 197, Garrison skillfully executes the C Locrian mode for four measures, in mm. 205 to 207, he continues to demonstrate his mastery the fluidity of notes under the Eb Dorian mode; Garrison also uses the 4ths interval of sequence to create the bass line. From mm. 209 to 216, Garrison employs a walking bass line in Eb Dorian, during this process, Garrison also uses a chromatic approach from mm. 211 to 215.

197

201 *Eb m^{6/9}* Loerian mode

205 sequence

209 *Eb m^{6/9}* Chromatic approach

213 Dorian mode

Figure 4.33 “Resolution,” mm. 197–216.

In this section, notable alterations were made to the rhythm. Garrison employed the Eb Aeolian mode from mm. 241 to 243, consistently emphasizing Eb with eighth notes, except for occasional chromatic approach processing and sequences. Moreover, Garrison incorporated more high notes into his performance, repeating Eb notes to enhance the timbre nature of the rhythm from mm.254 to 257.

The image displays a musical score for a bass line, consisting of five staves of music. The key signature is E-flat major (three flats: B-flat, E-flat, A-flat). The time signature is 4/4. The score is annotated with measure numbers 241, 245, 249, 253, and 257. A bracket under the first staff (measures 241-244) is labeled "Aeolian mode". A bracket under the fourth staff (measures 253-256) is labeled "root emphasis". The notation includes various rhythmic values such as quarter, eighth, and sixteenth notes, as well as rests and ties.

Figure 4.34 “Resolution,” mm. 241–260.

In sections of mm.261 to 284, Garrison generates the bass line, facilitating the chromatic approach and introducing distinctive tonal qualities that contrast with the harmonic backdrop in m.273. Additionally, in m. 278, Garrison skillfully uses the Eb Aeolian mode for the melody, using a repeated note to build a descending sequence pattern.

261

265

Dorian mode

269

273

3
arpeggio

277

double note

281

Figure 4.35 “Resolution,” mm. 261–284.

The bass line in C Locrian mode returns to the thematic melody, mirroring the initial tune. Garrison employs the double stop technique, modifying it with dotted quarter notes while adjusting intervals according to the root, 5th, and octave, with all motifs in Eb Dorian.

285
Ebm⁹ Locrian mode B⁹(sus4)

289
melody reprise F⁷alt. Dorian mode Bb⁷alt. Fm Bb⁷alt.

293

297
Ebm⁹ double stops B⁹(sus4)

301
F⁷alt. arpeggio Bb⁷alt.

Figure 4.36 “Resolution,” mm. 285–304.

The tempo gradually slows, transitioning into a free tempo after the theme concludes, ultimately leading to its conclusion.

305 Ebm⁹ double stops B⁷(sus4) 3

309 F⁷alt. Dorian mode Ebm([#]11) Ebm⁹

313 Ebm⁹ double stops double stops B^b7alt.

317 Ebm⁹ free tempo

321 slowing down double stops

Figure 4.37 “Resolution,” mm. 305–324.

4.3 Analysis of Christian McBride’s style in “My Favorite Things”

4.3.1 Introduction to “My Favorite Things”

“My Favorite Things” is a renowned composition that holds a significant place in music history. This melody initially debuted in the movie *The Sound of Music*, and while John Coltrane's rendition remains widely recognized, the Christian McBride Trio presents a fresh interpretation on their album *Out Here*. They genuinely showcase their musical creativity by incorporating a 5/4-time signature, intricate arrangements, and more improvisational solos.

In this composition, the use of a 5/4-time signature prompts McBride to predominantly maintain a stable groove while incorporating a feature that follows a 3+2 pattern.

Figure 4.38 Signature of 5/4.

4.3.2 Analysis of “My Favorite Things” Bass Lines

In the opening section, Christian McBride establishes the tonal center by sustaining the root note of E, which serves as the fundamental key throughout the composition. This prolonged note duration resembles a piano's sustained pedal, enhancing the overall sound and providing robust support for the accompaniment. In m. 5, McBride introduces a development in E by employing the E minor pentatonic scale. This choice not only adds harmonic richness in conjunction with the piano, but also establishes E minor pentatonic as a prominent bass line scale within this composition. Subsequently, McBride expands upon this scale by adding additional notes to form an E Aeolian mode, further intensifying its ethereal characteristics. In m. 12, McBride employs a motif consisting of several notes to establish a rhythmic foundation for comping, and the melodic materials that follow are all derived from variations on the E minor pentatonic scale.

Intro

Em⁷

Pedal

5

E minor pentatonic scale

E Aeolian mode

9

13

E minor pentatonic scale

17

Figure 4.39 “My Favorite Things,” mm. 1–20.

Section A introduces the thematic melody, with McBride extending the preceding motif and establishing a rhythmic foundation beneath it. At m. 28, McBride introduces an unexpected change by incorporating quarter note triplets. Following this groove section, chords shift as McBride employs arpeggiated triads and executes rapid unison with other instrument parts, creating a striking contrast. After a brief interlude, McBride resumes playing the groove while utilizing the E minor pentatonic scale and introducing subtle variations in note selection.

Figure 4.40 “My Favorite Things,” mm. 21–36.

In section B, McBride maintains the groove under Em7 as previously established; however, a notable difference occurs in m. 44, where the triplet is replaced with eighth notes. The overall groove undergoes slight modifications in note selection, incorporating all Am7 chord tones in an ascending arpeggio in m. 45.

Figure 4.41 “My Favorite Things,” mm. 37–48.

The C section features a key change. The second theme melody differs significantly from the first. Notably, in m. 48, there is a key change to the Bb major,

distinguishing it from the rest of the tune. From m. 49 to m. 60, McBride skillfully plays only the high-pitched octave of the Bb note, creating a break in the music. This section is played with freedom and supports the piano solo. After the piano solo concludes, McBride continues playing the theme melody under an Ebmaj7 chord. In the whole C section, not only does the bass play the same melody as the piano, but it also switches back to the original key. What is truly remarkable is that McBride introduces a counterpoint against the piano in m. 66, adding an element of surprise to accompany the theme melody. Following this passage, McBride resumes his usual rhythm and moves on to the next part.

49 **C**

53 octave groove

57

61 Ebmaj7 Eb+7

65 Am7 D7 Gmaj7 Cmaj7 Gmaj7 Cmaj7 F#m7(b5) B7(b9)

unison counterpoint

Figure 4.42 “My Favorite Things,” mm. 49–68.

Although the D section returns to the theme melody, it exhibits a heightened sense of intensity. McBride deliberately opts for lower-pitch notes in this section, maintaining the same rhythmic groove and melodic structure as before. However, he incorporates additional triplet quarter notes and plays with greater force.

69 **D** Em⁷

73 Em⁷

77 Em⁷ E minor pentatonic scale

81 Am⁷ D⁷ Gmaj⁷ Cmaj⁷ Gmaj⁷ Cmaj⁷ F#m⁷(b5) B⁷(b9)

arpeggio

Figure 4.43 “My Favorite Things,” mm. 69–84.

The E section remains consistent with the John Coltrane’s version of the “My Favorite Things” B section. Yet, the McBride trio employs a distinct approach to its execution, sustaining the preceding segment's fervor while infusing it with elements reminiscent of rock music. The comping retains the fundamental rhythm but incorporates subtle alterations. McBride utilizes eighth-note quadruplets and replaces the expected two dotted quarter-notes in m. 90. Additionally, he employs sequences from the E minor scale to substitute chord tones, enhancing the bass line's flexibility and dynamism. McBride introduces diverse rhythms throughout, exemplifying over unconventional time signatures such as 5/4.

E

85 Em⁷ C[#]ø⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷ 3

89 Em⁷ C[#]ø⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷ groove

93 Em⁷ C[#]ø⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷ variation

97 Em⁷ C[#]ø⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷ sequence

101 Em⁷ C[#]ø⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷ variation

105 Am⁷ B^bø⁷ G/B Cm⁶ groove C[#] Cm/D Dm

109 Em⁷

Figure 4.44 “My Favorite Things,” mm. 85–112.

CHAPTER V

APPLICATION TO PRACTICE

After transcription, analysis, and practice, the author found inspiration from the three bassists comprising the present study, leading to significant performative activities. These include making arrangements for the recital, featuring aspects of the bass line, and soloing. The following sections discuss the adaptation of the four songs.

5.1 “Dear Old Stockholm”

5.1.1 The Bass Lines

The author has drawn from the Paul Chambers bass line and modified it. In the first bar, the notes C# and D# are two chromatic notes around D (refer to Figure 24, m.72). In the second bar, E Locrian is used before resolving on the 3rd (Bb) of Gm7 and transitioning to the F Ionian in m. 4. MM. 5 to 6 feature a similar bass pattern. At the same time, measure 8 showcases a triplet that leads elegantly from mm. 7 to 8. Finally, mm. 9 to 12 integrate elements of the original bass line with a counterpoint against the thematic melody.

Figure 5.1 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 1–12.

In the area of mm.13 to 24, the author utilizes arpeggios to construct the bass line and raise its pitch. The author also employs rootless voicings in mm. 15 under C7, shifting the notes to the 3rd and 5th of C7(refer to Figure 23, m. 61). Additionally, these leaps imbue the bass line with greater dynamism. Following a triplet in m.16, the bass line ascends to a higher register and employs approach tones to craft a melodic contour. From mm. 21 to 24, the bass lines continue using the original pattern while creating a counterpoint with the thematic melody.

Figure 5.2 shows three staves of bass line notation for measures 13-24. The first staff (measures 13-16) includes chords: Dm arpeggio, Eø7, A7, Gm7, C7 rootless, and Fmaj7. A triplet of eighth notes is marked in measure 16. The second staff (measures 17-20) includes chords: Eø7, A7, Dm, Eø7, and A7. The third staff (measures 21-24) includes chords: Dm7, Dm6, Dm7(b5), and Dm6. The notation is in bass clef with a key signature of one flat.

Figure 5.2 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 13–24.

In the area of mm.25 to 28, the author utilizes the enclosure from F to G (mm.25 to 26), followed by employing chord tones to facilitate a clear harmonic progression and structure in the bass line.

Figure 5.4 shows a single staff of bass line notation for measures 25-28. The notation is in bass clef with a key signature of one flat. Chord symbols above the staff are: Fmaj7, Gm7, C7, Fmaj7, Eø7, and A7.

Figure 5.4 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 25–28.

In the area of mm.29 to 43, mm. 29 to 30 utilize the D harmonic minor scale, incorporating a passing note around A and a movement to G in m. 31. Additionally, from mm. 31 to 34, the bass line transitions from the F Ionian mode to the D harmonic

minor scale. Beneath the C7 chord from mm. 35 to 40, the bass line exclusively plays G and C in response to changes in the thematic melody.

Figure 5.5 “Dear Old Stockholm,” mm. 29–43.

5.2 “Soul Eyes”

5.2.1 The Bass Lines

In the context of this ballad, the author has integrated the basic two-feel with various rhythms, including the eighth-note triplet and sixteenth-notes.

In the area of mm.1 to 8, the bass line is constructed from chord tones. For instance, in m. 1, C and Eb are chord tones while F and F# function as chromatic approaches to G (refer to Figure 27, m. 5). In m. 3, triplets are employed along with scale movement to reach F. In m. 5, triadic quarter notes combined with triplets contribute to a more fluid and nonrestricted bass line. A departure from the two-feel is introduced in m. 6 by prolonging the root note and utilizing E and F# as characteristic notes for constructing the altered Bb scale. Finally, mm. 7 and 8 feature the Db note shared by the Gm7b5 and C7b9 chords.

Figure 5.6 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 1–8.

In the area of mm.9 to 16, it is typical to incorporate a spectrum of rhythmic variations. For example, in m. 9, the transition from Ab to C is achieved through sixteenth notes. Similarly, in m. 10, emphasis on the D note is attained through syncopation following a chromatic approach. In m. 12, after establishing triplet connections, there is a significant diversification of rhythm involving not only quarter notes but also eighth notes. In mm. 13 to 15, the bass lines are characterized by ascending and descending movements within the context of the Gb Ionian mode (refer to Figure 34, m. 57). Finally, in m. 15, the bass line descends sequentially.

Figure 5.7 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 9–16.

In the area of mm.17 to 24, m. 17 utilizes quarter notes and eighth notes to construct the scale, while mm. 18 to 21 maintain the previous rhythm of triplet eighth notes and syncopation. In m. 22, the Bb7 whole-tone scale produces a robust sound under the chord. Additionally, m. 23 employs the G Phrygian mode for a seamless transition to C.

17 Cm7 G7(b9) Cm7 F7(#11)

21 Fm7 Bb7alt Gm7(b5) C7(b9)

whole-tone scale G Phrygian mode

Figure 5.8 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 17–24.

The area of mm.25 to 32 features more triplet quarter notes to enhance the freedom of the bass line and syncopation was employed using both quarter and half notes. In m. 28, an arpeggio fully outlines the C7b9 chord from root to b9 note, and similarly, another arpeggio is used to construct a bass line for Bb7 from root to b7 note in m. 30.

25 Abmaj7 D7(b9) Gm7(b5) C7(b9)

arpeggio

29 Fm7 Bb7alt Ebmaj7 Dm7(b5) G7(b9)

arpeggio

Figure 5.9 “Soul Eyes,” mm. 25–32.

5.3 *A Love Supreme* “Part II: Resolution”

5.3.1 The Bass Lines

The “Resolution” theme consists of 24 bars with chord changes based on the Eb minor scale. For the melody section, the author creates the bass line to align with the melodic changes, utilizing frequent dotted quarter notes and predominantly employing root and 5th notes. The overall composition is played in a Latin-like groove style, incorporating eighth notes to embellish the root note and emphasize the rhythm. Additionally, double stops akin to Jimmy Garrison’s appear in m. 24 but use the interval of a 5th. As a result, the bass line for the theme emphasizes the groove and closely follows thematic changes.

The musical score for the bass line of "Resolution" in Eb minor, measures 1-24, is as follows:

- Measures 1-4: Ebm^{6/9} (Chord change at m. 1)
- Measures 5-8: Fm^{7(b5)} (Chord change at m. 5)
- Measures 9-12: Ebm (Chord change at m. 9)
- Measures 13-16: Fm⁷ (Chord change at m. 13)
- Measures 17-20: Bb^{7alt.} (Chord change at m. 17)
- Measures 21-24: Ebm (Chord change at m. 21)

Figure 5.10 “Resolution,” mm. 1–24.

For the accompanying part, the chord changes are based on the Eb minor scale, allowing for greater freedom in the harmonic section. The author has adjusted the scale: mm. 25 to 28, using the Eb Aeolian mode and incorporating triplet notes and skips to create broader melodic movements. From mm. 29 to 32, the scale shifts to Eb harmonic minor scale; from mm. 33 to 36, it transitions to the Eb whole tone scale; and from mm. 37 to 40, it changes to Eb Phrygian mode. Additionally, double stops are employed to enhance the melodic harmony scale (refer to Figure 45, m. 156). In mm. 41 to 44, there is a shift toward using an Eb minor pentatonic scale. Later, mm. 45-48 introduce more dynamic elements, emphasizing a groovier bass line, highlighting Eb. These sections use triplets and skips extensively for wide-ranging note movements and enhanced rhythmic dynamism.

The musical score consists of six staves of bass clef notation in Eb minor. Each staff is labeled with a measure number and a scale or mode name. Brackets and the number '3' indicate triplet passages.

- Staff 1 (mm. 25-28):** Labeled "Eb \flat m \flat ". A bracket spans measures 25-28 with a "3" below it, indicating a triplet.
- Staff 2 (mm. 29-32):** Labeled "Eb aeolian mode". A bracket spans measures 29-32 with a "3" below it, indicating a triplet.
- Staff 3 (mm. 33-36):** Labeled "Eb \flat m \flat " and "Eb harmonic minor scale". A bracket spans measures 33-36.
- Staff 4 (mm. 37-40):** Labeled "Eb whole tone scale". A bracket spans measures 37-40.
- Staff 5 (mm. 41-44):** Labeled "Eb \flat m". A bracket spans measures 41-44 with a "3" below it, indicating a triplet.
- Staff 6 (mm. 45-48):** Labeled "Eb minor pentatonic scale". A bracket spans measures 45-48.

Figure 5.11 "Resolution," mm. 25–48.

5.4 “My Favorite Things”

5.4.1 The solo

For this composition, the focus of the solo section is to imitate Christian McBride's bass solo style. This bass solo is based on the E Aeolian mode, with the 5/4 time signature permitting more flexible rhythmic expression. The arrangement aims to explore innovative rhythmic patterns within the framework of the E Aeolian mode.

In mm. 1 to 3, a motif is introduced for the entire solo section and subsequently developed. It commences on the B note in m.2 and follows the E aeolian mode. In mm. 8 to 10, the B Phrygian mode is employed before resolving on the 5th note of Em. The motif reemerges with a repetition of its initial melody, culminating in measure 18, where it resolves on the root note in comparison with the preceding material. Following two development measures, the melody takes a new direction, ascending in E aeolian from mm. 19 to 23. Upon conclusion of this segment, the motif resurfaces once more with a repeat performance of the original melody.

The entire section maintains a consistent rhythm during the solo, followed by a two-bar pause after a phrase end. This creates a sense of silence within the 4/5-time signature and gradually shifts the mood from tranquility to intensity, mirroring the original tune.

The image displays a musical score for the piece "My Favorite Things" in bass clef, 5/4 time, spanning measures 1 to 34. The key signature is one sharp (F#). The score is divided into eight systems, each starting with a measure number. The notation includes various rhythmic patterns, such as quarter notes, eighth notes, and sixteenth notes, often grouped with slurs and ties. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-4. Specific technical markings include a 4-measure rest in measure 1, and several triplet and quadruplet markings. The piece concludes with a double bar line at the end of measure 34.

Figure 5.12 "My Favorite Things," mm. 1–34.

CHAPTER VI

RECITAL INFORMATION

This chapter presents a comprehensive overview of the author's recital, encompassing details of location, duration, participating musicians, and jury members, as well as a list of instruments and equipment utilized in the performances discussed in the preceding chapters.

6.1 Recital Details

Recital name: Jazz Bass Master's Recital by Guodong Yang

Location: Room A113, College of Music Mahidol University

Musicians: Guodong Yang - Bass, ZhengWei Huang - Saxophone, Sirawet Sripuksachard - Piano, Jiahe Geng - Drums

Committee Members: Lect. Dr. Tanarat Chaichana, Lect. Darin Pantoomkomol, Asst. Prof. Krit Buranavitayawut

Date and time: Thursday, March 14, 2024, 12:00pm

Recital video link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Jo_LXVID1Kw

6.2 Technical Information

The concert took place in Room A113, Building A, a spacious and well-lit classroom ideal for jazz performances. On the day of the performance, preparations were made an hour in advance to ensure everything was set up properly. This included adjusting the piano position, setting up the drums, two monitoring speakers, bass speakers, piano microphone, and bass microphone to ensure a punctual start.

During the performance, there was a minor issue with microphone feedback which was promptly addressed and resolved. The overall performance proceeded smoothly without any errors or interruptions.

Regarding equipment aside from the musicians' own bass pickups, cymbals, and snare drums, all other necessary items were rented from Mahidol Music College's Equipment Management Room.

6.3 Program Notes and Recital Posters

**Guodong Yang's
Master Jazz Bass Recital**

Piano-Sirawet Sripuksachard
Saxophone-Zhengwei Huang
Drums-Jiahe Geng

March 14th, 2024
Building A Room A113

Program Notes

My favorite thing

Whatever the area of popular or jazz, *my favorite thing* is a famous song from the whole music history. This tune first appeared in the movie *The Sound of Music*. As we all know, the famous version is John Coltrane's recorded version, but on the album *OUT HERE* by Christian McBride, Trio. This band uses a new way of expressing the classical song, based on 5/4 beats with more arrangement and free solos. It totally shows the creative side of music.

All or nothing at all

This tune was composed by Arthur Altman in 1939. It has a clear form in AABA and is between the keys of A minor and A major. In 1962, Coltrane recorded this song again and added a new arrangement with more groove. Until today, many jazz musicians have played this tune, like Kurt Rosenwinkel, Morten Hasbøl, Jonathan Kreisberg, and Ari Hoenig.

Dear Old Stockholm

It's a folk song from Swedish also it's a very classical song in jazz history, so many jazz masters, including Miles Davis, John Coltrane, Red Garland Paul Chambers, etc. Especially for John Coltrane, he had recorded this song in different years, and the remarkable version is played with Roy Haynes. Haynes gave a special feel like a spreading, a permeating. Complete Coltrane's music at all.

Soul Eyes

This song is a composition with lyrics written by Mal Waldron, its form is ABAC with 32 bars on 4/4 time and ballad style, in 1962 John Coltrane recorded the tune in his album *Coltrane*, and it's the second time to record this tune after that, *Soul eyes* became a jazz standard tune and recorded by different musicians.

A love supreme part II: Resolution

A Love Supreme is widely regarded as one of the greatest jazz albums in history, primarily due to its groundbreaking musical innovations, spiritual depth, and profound influence on the genre. The album was released in 1965 and recorded by John Coltrane, McCoy Tyner, Jimmy Garrison, and Elvin Jones, which proves Coltrane's contribution to the jazz world.

Introduction

2015-2019: studied music education at Yunman Art University.
 2018 started learning jazz bass with Mr. Min Yi.
 2021 the "Bass-China" competition, won the award for Best Jazz Performance and studied jazz bass with Mr. Lyman Medeiros.
 2022, come to Mahidol University Music College and study jazz with Tanarat Chaichana Noppadol Tirataradol Porchai Vajyapark Krit Kurannavitayawat Kom Wongsawat and Sarute Wijitwechakarn etc.

Acknowledgement

Family—I am very thankful to my family, who have always supported me, respected my choices, and never stopped me from doing what I wanted to do.

Tanarat Chaichana—I am very thankful to Mr. Tanarat Chaichana for guiding me during my period at Mahidol University and being my mentor during my postgraduate life. Mr. Tanarat is very responsible and taught me with a lot of patience. Whatever problems, he always uses the nicest way and tells me as many details as he can. It is really encouraging my life in any aspect and influencing my attitude towards music and other things.

Teammates—I'd like to express my gratitude to my teammates who performed in my recital, used normal time to have a rehearsal with me, and spent energy on my recital.

Finally, very thanks to **Ajan William** and **Ajan Darin** for taking the time to join my recital and give advice.

MAHIDOL UNIVERSITY
 JAZZ DEPARTMENT, COLLEGE OF MUSIC, MAHIDOL UNIVERSITY

JAZZ BASS MASTER RECITAL

Guodong Yang

March 14th 2024
 12:00 pm Thursday

Building A
 room A113

Sax
 Zhanqun Huang

Piano
 Jiayu Qiang

Piano
 Sirawat Sripankasasara

CHAPTER VII

CONCLUSION

A comprehensive study and analysis of the bass line features and stylistic approaches of Paul Chambers, Jimmy Garrison, and Christian McBride across different periods has yielded significant research findings.

7.1 Summary of the Three Bassists' Styles

Whether in a bass solo or comping, the three bass masters all demonstrated similar technical skills. However, due to stylistic differences, each of the three bass players imbued their unique personality into their bass lines.

1) Paul Chambers's solo predominantly follows the chord changes, and his melody exhibits a strong structural form. The solo emphasizes a single scale. Additionally, there are well-crafted breaks in the solo where the melody pauses at strategic points, effectively showcasing the characteristic features of the 1950s.

2) Jimmy Garrison's comping demonstrates a greater sense of freedom, as evidenced by his use of triplets and arpeggios to create a more liberated rhythm. His proficiency in double stops is particularly noteworthy, contributing to the distinctive style evident in his music. Regarding note choice, he strives to craft unique sounds and bass lines that align with the chord changes typical of jazz standards, allowing for increased creative expression within this framework.

3) As a band leader, Christian McBride demonstrates exceptional musical prowess, not only in his bass line but also in his arrangements. Through analysis, it is evident that McBride possesses remarkable versatility, seamlessly transitioning between various music styles. His bass line stands out for its distinctive groove, particularly evident in the 5/4 time signature, where he not only maintains stable patterns but also

incorporates diverse variations. In essence, McBride's bass line encompasses all possibilities within his music.

7.2 Comprehensive Methods Used in Author's Bass Lines

1) Paul Chambers' approach has greatly influenced the author's understanding of how to structure bass lines across multiple bars. His concept of combining two bars using a single scale has expanded the author's ability to think beyond conventional phrasing, allowing for smoother transitions and more fluid movements. Additionally, the rootless technique he employed has given the author new ways to emphasize chord tones while creating distinct and varied sounds within the bass line. The author can introduce more harmonic depth and nuance into my playing by focusing on chord tones rather than just the root. Another invaluable technique the author adopted from Chambers is the chromatic approach in the bass line. This allows for a more seamless and continuous motion between notes, providing an almost effortless flow that makes the overall progression feel natural and smooth.

2) The author learned from Jimmy Garrison has opened my mind to more creative possibilities within the bass. Garrison's use of free rhythm when accompanying a melody has encouraged bass players to break free from the constraints of strict timing. Rhythm can be an expressive tool, one that can shift and evolve to serve the music's emotional intent. When it comes to playing a walking bass line, his idea of switching between different scales within a single chord has brought a newfound flexibility to playing. This allows for the creation of more dynamic and varied bass lines, enabling the author to explore different tonalities while maintaining the harmonic integrity of the piece. Furthermore, Garrison's use of double stops—playing two notes simultaneously—has introduced me to a technique that adds layers of harmonic richness. Through this, the author learned how to support the harmonic structure and create a more textural, resonant sound.

3) Christian McBride has been a key figure in teaching the author the power of groove and its role in constructing melodic ideas. From McBride, the author absorbed the importance of drawing inspiration from the groove itself, using it as a foundation upon which melodies can be built. His approach has shown that melody and groove are

deeply intertwined—changing the groove can inspire entirely new melodic directions. The author also learned that shaping melodies to highlight the rhythmic features of the groove, creates a more compelling and cohesive musical statement. Perhaps most importantly, McBride has taught the author to be fearless in music—to embrace experimentation and to challenge the boundaries of what’s considered traditional. His philosophy of pushing the limits and daring to explore uncharted musical territory has profoundly influenced the author’s mindset, encouraging seeking new ways to innovate and express musicians through music.

7.3 Further Studies

In addition to studying under renowned bass masters, the author also aims to explore diverse musical genres to enhance his comprehensive understanding and proficiency in music. This will entail analyzing the techniques and styles of musicians from various historical periods and cultural backgrounds. The author is committed to delving deeper into the complexities of music theory, encompassing chord progressions, scales, and principles of composition. Furthermore, the author intends to actively seek opportunities for practical experience by collaborating with a wide range of musicians. The author aspires to refine his instrumental skills and gain valuable insights into the creative process by participating in live performances, recording sessions, and jam sessions. Additionally, the author is eager to experiment with novel sounds and instruments as a means of broadening his musical horizons. Ultimately, the objective of this study is not only to emulate esteemed bass masters but also to cultivate a distinctive musical style of the author’s style.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A

Transcription of “Dear Old Stockholm”

Played by Paul Chambers

The musical score is written in bass clef with a 4/4 time signature. It consists of ten staves of music, each with chord annotations above the notes. The key signature has one flat (B-flat).

- Staff 1:** Chords: Dm⁷, Dm⁶, Dm⁷, Dm⁶. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.
- Staff 2:** Chord: C^{7(sus4)}. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.
- Staff 3:** Chords: C^{7(sus4)}, A^{7(b9)}, Dm. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.
- Staff 4:** Chords: Dm, E^{ø7}, A⁷, Gm⁷, C⁷. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.
- Staff 5:** Chords: Fmaj⁷, E^{ø7}, A⁷, Dm, E^{ø7}. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.
- Staff 6:** Chords: A⁷, Dm⁷, Dm⁶, Dm⁷. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.
- Staff 7:** Chords: Dm⁶, Dm, E^{ø7}, A⁷, Gm⁷, C⁷. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.
- Staff 8:** Chords: Fmaj⁷, E^{ø7}, A⁷, Dm, E^{ø7}. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.
- Staff 9:** Chords: A⁷, Dm⁷, Dm⁶, Dm⁷. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.
- Staff 10:** Chords: Dm⁶, Fmaj⁷, Gm⁷, C⁷, Fmaj⁷. Melody: Quarter notes G₂, A₂, B₂, C₃, D₃, E₃, F₃, G₃.

2

41 E^{ø7} A⁷ Dm E^{ø7} A⁷ Gm⁷ C⁷

45 Fmaj⁷ E^{ø7} A⁷ Dm C⁷(sus4)

49

53 C⁷(sus4) A⁷ Dm

57 Dm E^{ø7} A⁷ Gm⁷ C⁷ Fmaj⁷

61 E^{ø7} A⁷ Dm E^{ø7} A⁷

65 Dm⁷ Dm⁶ Dm⁷ Dm⁶

69 Dm E^{ø7} A⁷ Gm⁷ C⁷ Fmaj⁷

73 E^{ø7} A⁷ Dm E^{ø7} A⁷

77 Dm⁷ Dm⁶ Dm⁷ Dm⁶

81 Fmaj⁷ Gm⁷ C⁷ Fmaj⁷ E^{ø7} A⁷

85 Dm E \flat 7 A7 Gm7 C7 Fmaj7 3

89 E \flat 7 A7 Dm C7(sus4)

93

97 C7(sus4) A7 Dm

Detailed description: This block contains four staves of musical notation in bass clef with a key signature of one flat (B-flat). The first staff (measures 85-92) includes a measure number '85' and a '3' at the end. Chord symbols above the staff are Dm, E \flat 7, A7, Gm7, C7, and Fmaj7. The second staff (measures 89-92) includes a measure number '89' and chord symbols E \flat 7, A7, Dm, and C7(sus4). The third staff (measure 93) includes a measure number '93'. The fourth staff (measures 97-100) includes a measure number '97' and chord symbols C7(sus4), A7, and Dm. The notation consists of eighth and quarter notes, rests, and a double bar line at the end of the fourth staff.

Appendix B

Transcription of “Soul Eyes”

Played by Jimmy Garrison

The musical score is written in bass clef with a key signature of two flats (Bb and Eb) and a common time signature (C). It consists of ten staves of music, each containing a bass line with various chords and triplet markings. The chords are labeled above the notes, and the triplet markings are indicated by a '3' below the notes.

Staff 1: Cm7, G7(b9), Cm7, F7(#11)

Staff 2: Fm7, Bb7alt., Gm7(b5), C7(b9)

Staff 3: Abmaj7, Am7(b5), D7(b9), Gmaj7, Db7

Staff 4: Gbmaj7, Fm7, Bb7, Ebmaj7, Dm7(b5), G7(b9)

Staff 5: Cm7, G7(b9), Cm7, F7(#11)

Staff 6: Fm7, Bb7alt., Gm7(b5), C7(b9)

Staff 7: Abmaj7, D7(b9), Gm7(b5), C7(b9)

Staff 8: Fm7, Bb7alt., Ebmaj7, Dm7(b5), G7(b9)

Staff 9: Cm7, G7(b9), Cm7, F7(#11)

Staff 10: Fm7, Bb7alt., Gm7(b5), C7(b9)

Drum play Double time

2

41 $A\flat\text{maj}7$ $A\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $D7(\text{b}9)$ $G\text{maj}7$ $D\text{b}7$

45 $G\flat\text{maj}7$ $F\text{m}7$ $B\flat7$ $E\flat\text{maj}7$ $D\text{maj}7(\text{b}5)$ $G7(\text{b}9)$

49 $C\text{m}7$ $G7(\text{b}9)$ $C\text{m}7$ $F7(\#\text{11})$

53 $F\text{m}7$ $B\flat7\text{alt.}$ $G\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $C7(\text{b}9)$

57 $A\flat\text{maj}7$ $D7(\text{b}9)$ $G\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $C7(\text{b}5)$

61 $F\text{m}7$ $B\flat7\text{alt.}$ $E\flat\text{maj}7$ $D\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $G7(\text{b}9)$

65 $C\text{m}7$ $G7(\text{b}9)$ $C\text{m}7$ $F7(\#\text{11})$

69 $F\text{m}7$ $B\flat7\text{alt.}$ $G\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $C7(\text{b}9)$

73 $A\flat\text{maj}7$ $A\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $D7(\text{b}9)$ $G\text{maj}7$ $D\text{b}7$

77 $G\flat\text{maj}7$ $F\text{m}7$ $B\flat7$ $E\flat\text{maj}7$ $D\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $G7(\text{b}9)$

81 $C\text{m}7$ $G7(\text{b}9)$ $C\text{m}7$ $F7(\#\text{11})$

85 $F\text{m}7$ $B\flat7\text{alt.}$ $G\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $C7(\text{b}9)$

89 $A\flat\text{maj}7$ $A\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $D7(\text{b}9)$ $G\text{m}7(\text{b}5)$ $C7(\text{b}9)$ 3

93 $F\text{m}7$ $B\flat7\text{alt.}$ $E\flat\text{maj}7$ $B\text{maj}13(\sharp11)$
Arco

97 $E\flat\text{maj}7$

Appendix C

Transcription of “A Love Supreme Part II: Resolution”

Played by Jimmy Garrison

Ebm

bass intro

5

9

13

17 **Ebm⁹** **B⁷(sus4)**

sax melody

21 **F⁷(#⁹)** **Ebm** **B^b7^{alt.}**

25 **Ebm⁹** **B⁷(sus4)**

29 **F⁷(#⁹)** **F¹³(#⁹)** **B^b13(^b9)**

33 **Ebm⁹** **B⁷(sus4)**

37 **F⁷(#⁹)** **F⁷(#⁵)** **E⁶** **B^b7** **B^b13(^b9)**

2

41 *swing* Ebm⁹/₆ G⁷alt. Abm¹¹

bridge

45 E/Gb Ab(sus4)

49 Ebm⁹/₆ Ab¹³(b9) F⁷(#9) Ebm¹¹ E⁷(#9) G⁷(#9) A⁷(#9)

53 Bbm¹¹ Bm¹¹ Abm¹¹ Em¹¹ Dm¹¹ D⁷(sus4) Ebm¹¹ Bb¹¹ G⁷(#9)

57 Ebm¹³ B⁷(sus4)

melody reprise

61 F⁷(#9)₅ Ebm(#11) Ebm⁷(add11) Ebm¹³ B⁷alt.

65 Ebm¹³ B⁷(sus4)

69 F⁷(#9)₅ Bb(sus4)

73 Ebm¹³ B⁷(sus4)

77 F⁷(#9)₅ Ebm(#11)/Bb Ebm¹¹

81 *swing* Ebm⁹ B⁷

piano solo

85 $F7(\sharp 9)$ Ebm^{11} $Bb(sus4)$ 3

89 Ebm^{11} B^{13}

93 A^{13} G^{13} Bb^7

97 Ebm^{11} B^{13} A^{13}

101 $F7(\sharp 9)$ Bb^9 $Bb^7alt.$

105 Ebm^9 B^{13}

109 A^{13} G^{13} F^{13} Bb^{13}

113 Ebm^{11}

117

121 Ebm^6

125

4

129 Ebm¹¹

133

137 Ebm

141

145 Ebm

149 Ebm⁷

153 Ebm⁷ Ebm¹¹ C#m¹¹ D7(#9) Gm⁹ G7(#9) E13 A7(#9)

157 Bb⁹(#5)

161 Ebm⁹

165

169 Ebm⁹

173 B¹³ 5

177 Ebm^{6/9} Ebm¹¹ B¹³(#11)

sax solo

181 F⁷alt. Ebm¹¹ B⁷(#11)

185 Ebm^{6/9}

189 B⁷(#11)

193 Ebm^{6/9}

197

201 Ebm^{6/9}

205

209 Ebm^{6/9}

213

6 Ebm⁶

217

221

225 Ebm⁶

229

233

237

241

245

249

253

257

8

305 Ebm^{6/6} B^{7(sus4)}

309 F^{7alt.} Ebm^(#11) Ebm⁹

313 Ebm⁹ B^{b7alt.}

317 Ebm⁹

321 slowing down

Appendix D

Transcription of “My Favorite Things”

Played by Christian McBride

Intro

Em⁷

5

9

13

17

21 **A** Em⁷

Melody In

25 Em⁷

29 Am⁷ D⁷ G⁷ C⁷ D^b Free Break

33 Em⁷

37 **B** Em⁷

Detailed description: This is a bass clef musical score for the piece "My Favorite Things". It is written in 4/4 time and the key of E major (one sharp). The score is divided into several sections. The "Intro" section (measures 1-13) begins with an Em7 chord and features a melodic line with slurs and ties. Measure 5 has a "5" above it, and measure 9 has a "9" above it. Section "A" (measures 21-25) is marked with an "A" in a box and an Em7 chord. A "Melody In" instruction is placed between measures 21 and 25. Section 29 (measures 29-32) includes chords Am7, D7, G7, C7, and Db, and is labeled "Free Break". Section 33 (measures 33-36) is marked with an Em7 chord. Section "B" (measures 37-40) is marked with a "B" in a box and an Em7 chord.

2

41 Em⁷

45 Am⁷ D⁷ Gmaj⁷ Cmaj⁷ Gmaj⁷ Cmaj⁷ F#m⁷(b5) Bb(#11)

49 **C**

53

57

61 Ebmaj⁷ Eb⁺⁷

65 Am⁷ D⁷ Gmaj⁷ Cmaj⁷ Gmaj⁷ Cmaj⁷ F#m⁷(b5) B7(b9)

69 **D** Em⁷

73 Em⁷

77 Em⁷

81 Am⁷ D⁷ Gmaj⁷ Cmaj⁷ Gmaj⁷ Cmaj⁷ F#m⁷(b5) B7(b9)

E

85 Em⁷ C[#]o⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷ 3

89 Em⁷ C[#]o⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷

93 Em⁷ C[#]o⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷

97 Em⁷ C[#]o⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷

101 Em⁷ C[#]o⁷ Cm⁶ Cm⁶/B Am⁷

105 Am⁷ B^bo⁷ G/B Cm⁶ C[#] Cm/D Dm

109 Em⁷

BIOGRAPHY

NAME	Guodong Yang
DATE OF BIRTH	10 January 1996
PLACE OF BIRTH	Yunnan, China
INSTITUTIONS	Yunnan Art University, 2015-2019
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